

Title: Autonomous Cop Car

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INTRODUCTION:

Designing an Intelligent Control System which replicates the mechanism of a human brain in chasing a car. Knowledge from Mechatronics, Control System, Sensor Integration, Sensor Fusion, Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence are used to design the system.

AIM:

The aim is to make an electric car drive autonomous and chase a human controlled car.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

A Traxxas 4 tech 2.0 AWD electric car controlled by a 2.4GHz radio system is integrated with a microcontroller to generate the control signals. A vision sensor and LIDAR are integrated to the microcontroller. The data from both sensors are fused to make a control decision. Different methods from Machine learning and Artificial intelligence are used to achieve the output.

RESULTS:

A Microcontroller is integrated to generate the control signals which acts as the brain. A vision sensor is integrated to the microcontroller which replicates the human eye. The project is still in progress.

CONCLUSIONS:

Engineering is all about replicating the mechanisms of nature in a way to enhance the natural abilities and use them for the enrichment of human life

KEYWORDS:

Intelligent Control System, Mechatronics, Control Systems, Sensor Integration, Sensor Fusion, Machine Learning, Artificial Intelligence.

BIOGRAPHY:

Raghava Kalva is a passionate engineer who believes advancement in robotic technology enriches quality of human life. He is pursuing his Graduate Studies at University of Illinois at Chicago, Illinois, USA. Specializing in areas of Mechatronics, Control systems, Machine Learning, Computer Vision and Artificial Intelligence. He is a young engineer taking baby steps to make a difference to the world. His keen interest for engineering and technology drives him to take challenges in the field. Being Mechanical Engineering as his major in Undergraduate, he is pursuing his graduate studies in various majors and contributing his work in the field of Self Driving Cars.

